

Does the Family Environment and Entrepreneurship Education Promote Students' Entrepreneurial Intentions? The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Motivations

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Abstract

The goal of this research is to look at the effect of entrepreneurial education and the family environment on entrepreneurship motivation and intentions between students. This study includes 94 students of Muhadi Setiabudi University in various study programs who had taken entrepreneurship courses. Students with both a family background of entrepreneurship, both small and major businesses, seem to be the individuals who are chosen to be sampled. Questionnaires were used to obtain the data. The SmartPLS 3.0 application can then be used to process the data collected. The results in hypothesis testing show that entrepreneurial education has a positive and significant impact on students' motivation and intention to do business. While the family environment would have a positive effect on student motivation and entrepreneurship intentions, it did not have a significant effect. Policymakers and universities responsible for formulating policies or courses to encourage students to participate in entrepreneurial activities will find these insights helpful.

Keywords: *Family Environment, Entrepreneurial Education, Entrepreneurship Motivation, Entrepreneurship Intentions.*

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's entrepreneurship rate is roughly at 3.47 percent. According to Teten Masduki, Minister of Cooperative societies and MSMEs, the government set a national entrepreneurship ratio goal of 3.95 percent through 2024. When compared to neighboring countries such Malaysia and Thailand, this percentage is lower. And as far as strengthening and development of performance oriented young entrepreneurs is involved, Indonesia has enormous demographic potential. Universities, for example, have high-quality human resources (HR), makes it a great source for strengthening and developing productive entrepreneurs among millennials (economy.okezone.com).

Brebes Regency is one of the regions in Central Java Province with significant entrepreneurial potential; in addition to having the greatest population, it is also located between the mountains and the ocean, with the majority of residents being farmers and ranchers. The community's development of humanity's greatest possibilities will have a great economic worth. The Muhadi Setiabudi Brebes University was founded in order for citizens, particularly students, to help stimulate entrepreneurship and maximize the region's economic potential.

The goal of this research is to determine the impact of the family environment and entrepreneurial education on the motivation and entrepreneurial intentions of Muhadi Setiabudi University students, as well as to determine how the potential of the Brebes regency area, which is primarily comprised of MSMEs, can be developed for the better with creative and innovative entrepreneurs to increase people's income. Joko Widodo's presidential speech at the Indonesian Rectors Forum Conference (FRI) reaffirmed the importance of the entrepreneurial perspective in universities, saying that "the entrepreneurial perspective is very important so that universities can make various efforts sustainably in addition to expanding national insights," referring to Pancasila. 'Students should be educated in an ecosystem that supports socio-technical innovators by tackling social problems in an inventive and entrepreneurial manner using technology (Mudassir, 2021).

To all students in the study program, Muhadi Setiabudi University delivers entrepreneurship education courses and learning that relies on the cognitive, psychomotor, and affective worlds. Students are given the responsibility of creating business ideas and projects, in addition to receiving supplies, in order to promote motivation and entrepreneurial intents.

Educational variables, particularly the university environment, which fosters entrepreneurship in terms of knowledge and inspiration, can help students choose, entrepreneurial jobs and grow entrepreneurship as a result of the learning process (Akinbola et al., 2020; Hassan et al., 2021; Shabnaz & Islam, 2021). Entrepreneurship education is also allowed to contribute to long-term business success (Su et al., 2021). Furthermore, students' interest in choosing an

entrepreneurship, career is influenced by their family's entrepreneurial background (Mambu et al., 2019; Marhaini et al., 2014).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurial Intentions

In the psychological literature, the best predictor of a person's planned behavior is the intention. Entrepreneurship is a planned behavior because then every new business involves a lot of planning (Krueger et al., 2000). As stated by Hmieleski & Corbett (2006). Entrepreneurial intentions are the extent to which individuals have begun to plan for the creation of start-ups. Entrepreneurial intentions are identified as a student's desire to engage in entrepreneurial after graduation or a desire to work (Adekiya & Ibrahim, 2016).

Family Environment

The family environment is an entrepreneur closest social environment, so his role in shaping character, including the entrepreneurial character of a child, is important. (Marini & Hamidah, 2014). Interpersonal relationships between family members are a great resource for advice and support for new entrepreneurs. Access to information flows, such as markets, and technological knowledge, can be provided to family members (Aldrich & Cliff, 2003).

The family environment is divided into two types, namely the physical environment which includes learning resources and learning facilities, while the non-physical environment is in the form of parental guidance, compassion, parental support, and socioeconomic conditions (Indaryani et al., 2021). Research results from Susanto (2017) show that the higher the encouragement from the student family environment, the higher the interest in student entrepreneurship.

H1: The family environment has a positive and significant influence on entrepreneurial motivation.

H2: The family environment has a positive and significant influence on entrepreneurial intentions.

Entrepreneurship Education

According to Nursito and Nugroho (2013) in Anggraeni & Nurcaya (2016), entrepreneurship education in the form of science and understanding of entrepreneurship values, behaviors, and abilities in the presence of life's challenges. Entrepreneurial education is a center of learning activities Which will assist students in developing their skills through collaborative learning, emphasizing innovation, creativity, and networking. in the end, students have the potential to anticipate and predict future business opportunities (Mahendra et al., 2017).

High-quality programs will determine the types of Support services that can be used to help students succeed in starting a business (for example, consulting, advice, internship, mentoring). Finally, high-quality projects will show how research, scholarships, and teacher-related dedication activities can achieve the mission of the educational project (Vesper & Gartner, 1997). Souitaris et al. (2007) found that sensitization through a one-semester entrepreneurship program (January–May) resulted in stronger entrepreneurial intentions.

Study Galloway & Brown (2002) found that returns on investment in entrepreneurship education are more likely to be long-term than immediate. However, effective entrepreneurial education can be a factor to propel a person towards an entrepreneurial career (Henderson & Robertson, 2000). If universities provide sufficient knowledge and inspiration for entrepreneurship, the possibility of young people choosing entrepreneurial careers will increase. Community. These results confirm the critical role of education in developing entrepreneurial intentions.

H3: There is a positive and significant influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial motivation

H4: There is a positive and significant influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intentions

Entrepreneurial Motivations

Entrepreneurship motivation is self-encouragement, as a contribution of internal and external factors, allowing the growth of entrepreneurial intentions (Mahendra et al., 2017). Malebana (2014) found that Respondents' primary motivations for starting a business are the need to be independent (own boss), to challenge, to use their creativity, and secondly to need to make more money, they need to have an attractive job, the need to keep up with role models and market opportunities. According to Barba-Sánchez & Atienza-Sahuquillo (2018). There are three components of student entrepreneurial motivation: 1) Need independence, 2) Financial factors, 3) Need achievement.

Entrepreneurial motivation There is a significant positive effect on entrepreneurial intention and the third antecedent of entrepreneurial intention. Entrepreneurial motivation has a more significant impact on entrepreneurial attitude, followed by perceived behavioral control and entrepreneurial intention, and has the most negligible impact on subjective norms (Malebana, 2021). Entrepreneurship education is considered to enhance entrepreneurial motivation and to positively influence the entrepreneurial intention of an individual (Hassan et al., 2021; Mahendra et al., 2017). Meanwhile, to

encourage entrepreneurial intentions students need to do more intensive entrepreneurial education, encourage increased self-confidence, and foster entrepreneurship interest in the family environment (Sugianingrat et al., 2020).

H5: There is a positive and significant influence of entrepreneurial motivation on entrepreneurial intentions

H6: There is a positive and significant influence of the family environment on entrepreneurial intentions through entrepreneurial motivation

H6: There is a positive and significant influence of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial intentions through entrepreneurial motivation.

METHOD

Respondents in this study are students who have a background from an entrepreneurial family and have studied entrepreneurship courses at Muhadi Setiabudi University. Respondents consisted of 94 students from all study programs. Data analysis using a structural model with SmartPLS, using the outer and outer model test. The questionnaire consisted of demographic questions and structured research questions. A structured research question questionnaire with modified Likert type with 5 measurement scales (5=strongly agree, 4=agree, 3=neutral, 2=disagree, 1=strongly disagree). Family environment indicators adopted from research Susanto (2017), entrepreneurship education indicators adopted from research Anggraeni & Nurcaya (2016), indicators of entrepreneurial motivation adopted from research Barba-Sánchez & Atienza-Sahuquillo (2018), while the indicator of entrepreneurial intention was adopted from the research (Adekiya & Ibrahim, 2016). Constructs and indicators are found in table 1.

Table 1. Constructs and Indicators

Constructs	Indicators
Family Environment	1 I am involved in the family business
	2 I got my entrepreneurial briefing from a family business
Entrepreneurship Education	3 Entrepreneurship education is an important capital for success in entrepreneurship
	4 Entrepreneurship education is very important to be a provision in the future in entrepreneurship
	5 Entrepreneurship education can add knowledge and insight in entrepreneurship
	6 Entrepreneurship education provides ideas to minimize risk in entrepreneurship
	7 Entrepreneurship education fosters a desire for entrepreneurship
	8 Entrepreneurship education provides ideas for taking advantage of opportunities in entrepreneurship
Entrepreneurial Motivation	9 I developed myself into someone professional.
	10 I feel satisfied with my work
	11 I can change my environment
	12 I contribute to the welfare of society
	13 I have a good working relationship
Entrepreneurship Intention	14 I can achieve political and social power
	15 I am ready to be an entrepreneur
	16 My professional goal is to become an entrepreneur
	17 I will make every effort to start and run my own company
	18 I am determined to create a company in the future
	19 I am seriously thinking about starting a company
	20 I have a strong intention to start a company one day
	21 If I have the opportunity and the resources, I want to start a company
	22 Among the various options, I prefer to be an entrepreneur

Source: Data processing results, 2021

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Test

The outer model test shows each indicator relates to its latent variables. The analysis process is running algorithmic program calculations. Analysis results are used to determine whether the measurements used are worth measuring (valid and reliable). Several indicators, including convergent validity and discriminant

validity, can reflect the results of this reflective external model analysis.

The principle of convergent validity explains that a construct's manifest indicator should be highly correlated (Ghozali, 2015). According to Ghozali (2015) the rule of thumb is usually used to assess convergence validity. That is, the loading factor value must be greater than 0.7. And Average Variance Extracted (AVE), AVE describes the discriminant extracted on each indicator and you can know the ability of each item to be measured from other items. According to Ghozali (2015), the value of AVE should be greater than 0.5.

Furthermore, the Reliability test through the Comprehensive reliability test and Cronbach's Alpha By checking that all latent variable values have composite reliability values and Cronbach's Alpha must be greater than 0.7, it can be concluded that the questionnaire in this study is reliable as the constructor of the measurement tool. The results of validity and reliability are found in table 2.

Table 2. Measurement Outer Model

Variable	Indicators	Loading Factors	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Family Environment	FE4	0.713	0.395	0.764	0.620
	FE5	0.855			
Entrepreneurial Motivations	EM10	0.704	0.869	0.901	0.602
	EM2	0.764			
	EM3	0.866			
	EM4	0.777			
	EM5	0.794			
	EM6	0.742			
Entrepreneurial Intentions	EI1	0.744	0.915	0.930	0.626
	EI 3	0.773			
	EI4	0.815			
	EI5	0.772			
	EI6	0.845			
	EI7	0.815			
	EI8	0.708			
	EI9	0.848			
Entrepreneurship Education	ED1	0.801	0.889	0.914	0.639
	ED2	0.878			
	ED3	0.812			
	ED4	0.708			
	ED5	0.812			
	ED6	0.774			

Source: Data processing results, 2021

From the table above, it can be concluded that the measurement model in this study is acceptable. Among them, the composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach's Alpha values of the variables in the study are both greater than 0.7, unless the family environment is smaller than 0.7 which is 0.395. This confirms the reliability of a good research model. Furthermore, the AVE values of all variables in the study were greater than 0.5. All outer loading values of variables are also greater than 0.7 Which indicates that the research model has good convergent validity.

The validity of discriminants this can be seen in the Fornell Larcker Criterion test by comparing the square root of the AVE for each construct with the correlation value between the constructs in the model (Ghozali, 2015). A construct is declared valid if it has the square root from the highest AVE to the expected construct compared to the square root from the AVE to the other construct.

Table 3. Fornell Larcker Criterion

	FE	EM	EI	ED
Family Environment	0.787			
Entrepreneurial Motivation	0.333	0.776		
Entrepreneurial Intention	0.328	0.531	0.791	
Entrepreneurship Education	0.389	0.401	0.520	0.799

Source: Data processing results, 2021

According to the table above, the square root of AVE is a bold printed letter and the correlation seen from the diagonal. The square root of AVE should be greater than the correlation between the underlying structures.

Inner Model Test

The inner model test is based on the predictive capabilities of the research model as seen from the determinant coefficient value (R2), the significance level of the path coefficient (β), and T Statistic (Hair et al., 2014). The value of R-square (R2) is zero to one. As the value of R-squared (R2) approaches 1, the independent variables provide all the information needed to predict endogenous variables.

Figure 2. Inner Model

Source: Data processing results, 2021

The R2 values for two endogenous latent variables, entrepreneurial motivation, and entrepreneurial intentions were 0.197 and 0.398. The R2 value is categorized as quite moderate (Hair et al., 2014). This means that 19.7% of entrepreneurial motivation variables can be explained by family environment variables and entrepreneurial education. Meanwhile, the entrepreneurship intention variable is 39.8% can be explained by the variables of the family environment, entrepreneurial education, and entrepreneurial motivation.

Table 4. Inter-Construct Testing

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient (β)	T Statistic	P Value	Hypothesis Test Result
H1 FE → EM	0.208	1.674	0.095	Rejected
H2 FE → EI	0.071	1.286	0.199	Rejected
H3 ED → EM	0.329	3.315	0.001	Received
H4 ED → EI	0.344	4.926	0.000	Received
H5 EM → EI	0.369	4.384	0.000	Received

Source: Data processing results, 2021

The path coefficient (β) value is between -1 to +1, the value of +1 shows Strong positive correlation, -1 value indicates strong negative correlation (Hair et al., 2014). Referring to the table above generated path coefficient values (β) lead to strong positive relationships.

T-statistics are tested through bootstrapping procedures aimed at seeing significant value between constructs (Hair et al., 2014). The limits of rejected or accepted hypothesis are ±1.96, if the T-Statistical value is between -1.96 and 1.96, the hypothesis will be rejected.

Table 5. Mediation Interconstruct Testing

Hypothesis	T Statistic	P Value	Hypothesis Test Result
FE → EM → EI	1.407	0.199	Rejected
ED → EM → EI	2.927	0.001	Received

Source: Data processing results, 2021

Based on table 5, the results of the H1 and H2 hypothesis tests showed the absence of family environment toward entrepreneurial motivation ($\beta=0.208$, $T=1,674$, $P=0.095$) and family environment on entrepreneurial intentions ($\beta=0.071$, $T=1,286$, $P=0,199$) in Muhadi Setiabudi University students with entrepreneurial backgrounds. This is in line with the results of previous research conducted by (Indaryani et al., 2021; Sandi & Nurhayati, 2020; Wahyuni & Rismawati, 2020). The background of an entrepreneurial family does not determine a child has the motivation and intentions of entrepreneurship. This is because some of them are of the view that entrepreneurship has greater risks and challenges, fear of failure, and success in entrepreneurship tends to belong achieved and needs consistency. Therefore, this mindset is still the duty of society in general in increasing the level of entrepreneurship in Indonesia, especially in the Brebes Regency.

The results of the H3 hypothesis test Shows that entrepreneurial education has a significant positive impact on entrepreneurial motivation ($\beta=0.329$, $T=5,877$, $P=0.000$). Entrepreneurship education has a positive impact on increasing students entrepreneurship motivation. These findings are in line with the results of the study findings (Indaryani et al., 2021; Meitriana et al., 2020; Wahyuni & Rismawati, 2020). In entrepreneurship materials, there are ways to start entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial motivation, entrepreneurial characteristics, creativity and innovation, and how to prepare entrepreneurial proposals. The learning material provides an overview to become an entrepreneur and dare to entrepreneurship, then provides a new spirit for students.

The results of the H4 hypothesis test It shows that entrepreneurship education has a significant positive impact on entrepreneurial intention ($\beta=0.344$, $T=4,926$, $P=0.000$). Entrepreneurship education positively increases the entrepreneurship intentions of students. These findings are consistent with previous findings (Akinbola et al., 2020; Çera et al., 2021; Küttim et al., 2014). Boubker et al. (2021) direct learning and practice approaches that focus group discussions and simulations on business plan formulation are effective teaching methods. Therefore, entrepreneurial education programs for students for all study programs are an effective way to foster student entrepreneurship intentions.

The results of the H5 hypothesis test shows entrepreneurship motivation has a significant positive impact on entrepreneurial intentions ($\beta=0.369$, $T=4,384$, $P=0.000$). The existence of entrepreneurial motivations in students has proven to increase student entrepreneurship intentions. These findings are consistent with previous findings (Malebana, 2021; To et al., 2021). To et al.(2021) stated that entrepreneurship comes from two discrete variables: motivation and willpower. Entrepreneurship motivation is driven by cognition (entrepreneur's self-ability, beliefs and perception of market signals, etc.), and willpower is based on innate memory to regulate the influence-cognitive interaction (entrepreneurial, emotional, and reasoning orientation).

The results of the H6 hypothesis test showed the absence of the effect of mediation of entrepreneurial motivations between family environments on entrepreneurial intentions ($T = 1,407$ and $P = 1,199$). The entrepreneurial family environment cannot provide student entrepreneurial motivation, so entrepreneurial motivation cannot The relationship between intermediary entrepreneurial family environment and entrepreneurial intention. Most of them after graduating from college want to become professional employees who fit their chosen major. Students have not dared to become entrepreneurs because they need capital support, understand market opportunities, and the courage to look at business.

And then the results of the H7 hypothesis test showed the effect of The mediating effect of entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial motivation of entrepreneurial intention ($T =2,927$ and $P=0.001$). These findings are consistent with previous studies (Hassan et al., 2021; Solesvik, 2013). Entrepreneurship education has been proven to increase student entrepreneurship motivation, which in turn increases student entrepreneurship intentions. With the entrepreneurial knowledge possessed, it is hoped that it can shape the characteristics of entrepreneurial students who are creative and innovative.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it can be concluded that entrepreneurship education will affect students' motivation and entrepreneurial willingness. The family environment does not affect motivation and entrepreneurial intentions of students who have a family background in entrepreneurship. Therefore, to encourage entrepreneurial intentions of students need to be educated more intensively through business plan programs, business coaching, mentoring, making new products. Thus the entrepreneurship course program has a high contribution to the formation of students ready for entrepreneurship. While the family environment in this study is not a determining factor of

entrepreneurship students. Therefore, this mindset is still the task of society in general in increasing entrepreneurship..

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